

Optimal control of molecular spin qudits

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We demonstrate, numerically, the possibility of manipulating the spin states of molecular nanomagnets with shaped microwave pulses designed with quantum optimal control theory techniques. The state-to-state or full gate transformations can be performed in this way in shorter times than using simple monochromatic resonant pulses. This enhancement in the operation rates can therefore mitigate the effect of decoherence. The optimization protocols and their potential for practical implementations are illustrated by simulations performed for a simple molecular cluster hosting a single Gd^{3+} ion. Its eight accessible levels (corresponding to a total spin $S = 7/2$) allow encoding an 8-level qudit or a system of three coupled qubits. All necessary gates required for universal operation can be obtained with optimal pulses using the intrinsic couplings present in this system. The application of optimal control techniques can facilitate the implementation of quantum technologies based on molecular spin qudits.

I. INTRODUCTION

A crucial challenge for the development of quantum simulation and quantum computation is to scale up computational power while keeping the processor robust against noise and limiting the complexity of control lines and electronics [1–3]. A promising strategy is to replace qubits with d -dimensional ($d > 2$) quantum systems, or qudits [4–6], as the elementary building blocks of the quantum architecture. The ability to integrate nontrivial operations in a single physical system helps simplifying some quantum algorithms [7–9]. In addition, it can also facilitate their implementation by reducing the number of nonlocal operations, i.e. those connecting different parts of the circuit.

Qudits have been realized with the multiple quantum states of diverse physical systems, including photons [10], trapped ions [11], impurity nuclear spins in semiconductors [12] and superconducting circuits [13]. Here, we focus on a special class of systems, molecular nanomagnets [14–18] (see Fig. 1 for an illustrative example). These are coordination or supramolecular complexes that consist of a magnetic core surrounded by a shell of organic ligand molecules. Chemistry offers nearly unbound possibilities for the design of spin qudits based on these molecules. The combination of one or several $S > 1/2$ transition metal or lanthanide ions with sufficiently weak magnetic anisotropy and/or exchange interactions gives rise to a number of low-lying magnetic levels. For suitably chosen molecular structures, these levels are unequally spaced,

making transitions between them addressable via microwave resonant pulses. And nuclear spin states of the metal ions provide additional resources [19–23].

Examples of molecular based electronic and electronuclear spin qudits, with dimension d ranging from 4 up to 64, have been reported recently [19–30]. In addition, there have been proposals for exploiting their multiple states to specific applications. Relevant examples are the digital quantum simulation of spin-boson models [31], where the qudit encodes boson states, and the implementation of quantum error correction codes [30, 32, 33]. The latter is particularly promising, as embedding in each basic unit, in this case a molecule, a suitably designed protection against its specific decoherence sources might represent a huge competitive advantage. Besides, the functionalities need not be defined a priori. When the allowed transitions between different qudit states form a universal set, these systems can be regarded as microscopic size universal processors (or NISQs) [18, 22, 27–29, 34].

However, decoherence remains a serious limitation for fully unleashing the potential of these otherwise very appealing systems. Even though some specifically designed molecular spin qubits show remarkably long coherence times T_2 [35, 36], decoherence tends to increase for higher spin or molecules with a higher number of magnetic atoms. A sequence of necessarily imperfect gates might become impractically long as compared to T_2 , leading to large error rates. In the paradigmatic example of a qudit-based quantum error protocol, such effects can completely overcome the gain brought about by the code itself [30, 32]. Clearly, this calls for more efficient methods to carry out such operations.

In this work, we consider the possibility of applying quantum optimal control theory (QOCT) techniques [38,

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FIG. 1. *Top*: Schematic image of a molecular spin subject to a static magnetic field \vec{B} and to an arbitrarily shaped microwave magnetic field \vec{b} , here generated by a transmission line. *Bottom*: spin energy levels of the GdW_{30} polyoxometalate cluster [27, 37], whose structure is shown in the top. The 8 spin states, associated with the $S = 7/2$ spin of the central Gd^{3+} ion, enable encoding a $d = 8$ qudit or three qubits. The coloured circular arrows mark the seven transitions that can be implemented by means of resonant monochromatic pulses.

39] to mitigate some of the limitations associated with the use of monochromatic resonant pulses. The use of QOCT for the manipulation of spin systems was demonstrated in the field of nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) [40–44]. This theory allows designing more complex pulses in order to find the temporal shape of the external perturbation that makes the evolution operator equal to a predefined gate, as shown by Palao and Kosloff [45]. Numerous later calculations employing similar schemes have been reported [46–53]. We present here a modification of the method, that allows for the use of arbitrarily parametrized pulses, which permit to seamlessly impose constraints that match the experimental ones. We illustrate its application to the efficient control of molecular spin qudits by performing numerical simulations on

a $d = 8$ qudit encoded in the $S = 7/2$ spin states of a simple molecular cluster hosting a Gd^{3+} ion (Fig. 1) [37], for which a universal set of operations was realized experimentally [27]. We have parameterized the pulses using a range of different frequencies, and limiting the amplitude of each component (since otherwise the optimizations tend to favor high intensity solutions, that may be experimentally inaccessible, and moreover, would reduce the coherence times via the excitation of unwanted levels). The purpose is to assess the expected gains of using a multi-frequency setup, compared to the usual route to gate construction through simple monochromatic rotations.

The manuscript is organized as follows. In Section II we introduce the spin Hamiltonian describing the qudit, discuss standard control techniques based on monochromatic resonant pulses and its limitations in terms of operations speeds and fidelities, and describe the optimization methodology used in this work. Section III shows results obtained by these two methods and discusses their differences. Finally, Section IV summarizes the conclusions and future prospects derived from these results.

II. MODEL AND METHODOLOGY

A. Spin Hamiltonian: definition of qudit basis states

We consider a situation like that shown schematically in Fig. 1, where a molecular spin qudit is tuned by an external magnetic field \vec{B} and controlled by a time-dependent perturbation able to induce transitions between its different states. The underlying physics can be described by the following spin Hamiltonian

$$\hat{H} = \hat{H}_{\text{ZF}} + \hat{H}_{\text{Zeeman}} + \hat{H}_{\text{td}} \quad (1)$$

where \hat{H}_{ZF} is the zero-field spin Hamiltonian of the isolated molecule, \hat{H}_{Zeeman} is the Zeeman interaction with \vec{B} , and \hat{H}_{td} is a time-dependent control term. In general, \hat{H}_{ZF} can be quite complex and include the single ion anisotropy of the magnetic ions forming the molecular core, their mutual exchange and dipolar interactions as well as the hyperfine couplings to the nuclear spins. Yet, quite often this Hamiltonian can be simplified. This is the case when dealing with mononuclear molecules, hosting one metal ion, or when exchange interactions are sufficiently strong to ensure that only states with the lowest energy total spin value S are significantly populated at the relevant temperatures. The spin response can then be well approximated with the help of a “giant spin” approximation [14, 54]. In this work, we have used the following expressions for \hat{H}_{ZF} and \hat{H}_{Zeeman}

$$\hat{H}_{\text{ZF}} = D \left[\hat{S}_z - \frac{1}{3} S(S+1) \right] + E \left(\hat{S}_x^2 - \hat{S}_y^2 \right) \quad (2)$$

$$\hat{H}_{\text{Zeeman}} = -g\mu_B \vec{B} \hat{S} \quad (3)$$

where S is the spin quantum number of the molecule, $(\hat{S}_x, \hat{S}_y, \hat{S}_z)$ are the spin operators, D and E are magnetic anisotropy constants, g is the spin g -factor, and μ_B is the Bohr magneton. These expressions describe accurately the GdW₃₀ molecular spin qudit, which we use in section III below to illustrate the potential of QOCT techniques. In particular, the uniaxial magnetic anisotropy DS_z^2 provides the level anharmonicity that is required to properly address individual transitions between the qudit states. Yet, the methodology is general and could be applied to more complex versions of the spin Hamiltonian adapted to diverse implementations (e.g. those including weakly coupled electronic spins or a combination of nuclear and electronic spin states).

The last term in Eq. (1) provides the ability to control the quantum spin states. As with the static terms, for the sake of simplicity we use the following form

$$\hat{H}_{\text{td}} = -g\mu_B f(t) \vec{b} \hat{S} \quad (4)$$

which corresponds to a time-dependent version of the Zeeman interaction term (3). This Hamiltonian describes the most common spin control techniques, based on electron paramagnetic resonance methods, in which the absorption of this signal is the crucial observable. In recent times, it has been shown that spin qubits, including those in molecules, can also be manipulated by means of electric field pulses [55, 56]. In this case, the time-dependent perturbation introduces a modulation of the crystal field and the magnetic anisotropy terms associated with it. Again, the methods described below are easily adaptable to these situations.

B. Coherent control via monochromatic resonant pulses

Often, the temporal shape is a simple monochromatic term, e.g.

$$f(t) = \lambda \cos(\omega t + \phi) \Pi_{t_0}^{t_f}(t), \quad (5)$$

where the amplitude is determined by λ , and $\Pi_{t_0}^{t_f}$ is the rectangular function, that is equal to one if $t_0 \leq t \leq t_f$, and zero otherwise (in reality, of course, the ramp up and down at t_0 and t_f are not abrupt). If the frequency is chosen to be close to one of the resonances, and the amplitude is low enough, the rotating wave approximation (RWA) may be applied, and the effect of these pulses can be worked out analytically: if j, k are the two levels linked by the resonance (let us assume a perfect resonance, and that all other frequencies are well separated), the evolution operator $\hat{U}(t)$ is:

$$\hat{U}(t) = \hat{R}_{\vec{n}}^{(jk)}(\theta) \oplus \hat{I}^{(jk)}. \quad (6)$$

This expression assumes the interaction representation, and, in order to simplify the notation, we have set $t_0 = 0$.

The superindex (jk) on the two-dimensional *rotation* operator $\hat{R}_{\vec{n}}^{(jk)}(\theta)$ means that it acts on the subspace spanned by the j, k levels, whereas the rest of the levels are unaffected ($\hat{I}^{(jk)}$ is the identity in all but the j, k levels). Within the basis spanned by the two states, j, k , and the corresponding Pauli matrices σ_α (in that basis), the rotation operator is given by:

$$\hat{R}_{\vec{n}}(\theta) = \exp\left(-i\frac{\theta}{2}\vec{n} \cdot \hat{\sigma}\right). \quad (7)$$

$\hat{\sigma}$ is the vector of Pauli matrices. The rotation angle θ is $\lambda g \mu_B |\mu_{jk}| t$, where $\mu_{jk} = \langle j | \vec{b} \hat{S} | k \rangle$ is the coupling matrix element, and \vec{n} is the unit vector:

$$\vec{n} = (\cos(\arg \mu_{jk} + \phi), -\sin(\arg \mu_{jk} + \phi), 0). \quad (8)$$

The choice of ϕ determines the rotation axis: if $\phi = -\arg \mu_{jk}$, we have a $R_X(\theta)$ rotation; if $\phi = -\arg \mu_{jk} - \pi/2$, we have a $R_Y(\theta)$ rotation. We cannot have direct $R_Z(\theta)$ rotations, but they can however be built by combinations of the former two. We recall that here, X, Y, Z do not refer to any spatial direction, but to the Pauli matrices defined in the basis spanned by the states j, k .

Let us consider $R_X(\theta)$ rotations in the following. By adjusting the total pulse time t_f , one selects the angle θ and, for example, performs a π -rotation, i.e. if

$$t_f = t_\pi^\lambda = \frac{\pi}{\lambda g \mu_B |\mu_{jk}|} \quad (9)$$

the rotation transforms the j state into the k state and viceversa:

$$\hat{R}_X(\pi) = -i \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

Note the presence of the $-i$ factor; it is an irrelevant global phase factor if we consider the (j, k) subspace as isolated, but it changes the phase with respect to the rest of the levels.

In order to use these qudits as quantum information units, however, one needs the ability to perform arbitrary unitaries, and not only two-level rotations. Fortunately, by concatenation of several of these rotations, one may construct arbitrary unitaries in any 2^n -level system [18, 22, 27, 29, 57, 58] (Cf. Appendix A for details). The necessary sequences, as we shall show later in an example, may be long.

Furthermore, another problem that cannot be remedied is the approximate character of all previous expressions, that rely on the weakness of the perturbation amplitude λ , thus avoiding the possibility of arbitrarily speeding up the process by increasing that amplitude. If we require a minimum fidelity for the $|j\rangle \rightarrow |k\rangle$ transformations, then a minimum amount of time is necessary.

C. Quantum Optimal Control Theory (QOCT)

The previous arguments reveal an intrinsic limitation of monochromatic pulses for the creation of fast quan-

tum gates, which may be further complicated by the presence of experimental constraints, *i.e.* the inability to increase the magnetic field intensities. In order to create faster gates, one may attempt to use more complex temporal shapes, *i.e.* combine various frequencies. We therefore wonder how this possibility may help the control of molecular spin qudits, *i.e.* whether operation times can be made substantially shorter than the coherence times. For this purpose, we have applied QOCT. We summarize in the following the method and the basic equations that we have employed.

QOCT can be formulated in two different ways. One, the optimization of “point-to-point” or “state-to-state” transitions, *i.e.* the transfer of one particular initial state to a final one. Two, a “universal” optimization, *i.e.* the control of the full evolution operator of the process, which implies the full control of the evolution of any state. This last formulation is the one that one needs in order to find external couplings capable of generating quantum gates, and is therefore the one that we have focused on in this work. For this reason, this is the one that we describe below. However, since we also describe some state-to-state optimizations in the results section, we will also write at the end of this section the necessary equations for those calculations.

We consider that the time-dependent pulse-shape function $f(t)$ alluded above is parameterized with a set of values $u_0, \dots, u_M \equiv u$: *i.e.* $f = f(u; t)$. The evolution of the system is then determined by the Hamiltonian:

$$\hat{H}(u; t) = \hat{H}_0 + f(u; t)\hat{V}, \quad (11)$$

where $\hat{H}_0 = \hat{H}_{ZF} + \hat{H}_{Zeeman}$, and $\hat{V} = -g\mu_B\vec{S}\vec{b}$.

The evolution operator $\hat{U}(u; t)$ is thus also determined by u . In the interaction representation it evolves according to:

$$i\frac{\partial}{\partial t}\hat{U}(u; t) = f(u, t)\hat{V}(t)U(u; t), \quad (12)$$

$$\hat{U}(u; 0) = \hat{I}, \quad (13)$$

where $\hat{V}(t) = \exp(it\hat{H}_0)\hat{V}\exp(-it\hat{H}_0)$.

The goal is to find a set of parameters $u^{(0)}$ such that the evolution operator is equal – or equivalent – to a given target gate \hat{U}_G : $\hat{U}(u^{(0)}, T) = e^{ia}\hat{U}_G$ for any irrelevant global phase a . In the QOCT framework, this is achieved by finding a set of parameters that leads to the maximization of a functional of the system evolution; in this case this can be done by defining this functional as:

$$F(\hat{U}) = |\hat{U} \cdot \hat{U}_{\text{target}}|^2 \quad (14)$$

where the dot product in the space of linear transformations that we have used is the Fröbenius product:

$$\hat{A} \cdot \hat{B} = \frac{1}{d}\text{Tr}[\hat{A}^\dagger \hat{B}]. \quad (15)$$

Here, d is the space dimension. The functional thus defined acquires its maximum value (one) when \hat{U} is equal

to the target gate, modulo a phase factor. Since, as mentioned above, the evolution is determined by the parameters u , the problem is reduced to the maximization of the function:

$$G(u) = F[\hat{U}(u; t_f)]. \quad (16)$$

Many possible algorithms exist for finding the maxima of multivariate functions such as G . Most of them require to compute the gradient of the function (in addition to the function itself). Optimal control theory provides the mathematical tool to derive these gradients (essentially, Pontryagin’s maximum principle [59]). For the case of our function G , the gradient is given by:

$$\frac{\partial G}{\partial u_m}(u) = 2\text{Im} \int_0^{t_f} dt \frac{\partial f}{\partial u_m}(u; t)\hat{B}(u; t) \cdot (\hat{V}(t)\hat{U}(u; t)), \quad (17)$$

where the *costate* \hat{B} is defined by the following equations:

$$i\frac{\partial}{\partial t}\hat{B}(u; t) = f(u, t)\hat{V}(t)U(u; t), \quad (18)$$

$$\hat{B}(u; t_f) = (\hat{U}_{\text{target}} \cdot \hat{U}(t_f))\hat{U}_{\text{target}}. \quad (19)$$

Note that it is an equation of motion similar to the one that determines the evolution operator itself, except the boundary condition is given at the final time of the propagation t_f (it is a *final* condition, instead of an initial condition). In consequence, the computation of the gradient requires two propagations: a forward propagation for \hat{U} , and a backward propagation for \hat{B} .

It remains to specify the parametrization of f , an important task that actually defines the set of allowed temporal shapes. This should be done with the experimental limitations in mind. In our case, we have used two parametrizations. The first one is a simple Fourier expansion:

$$f(u, t) = f_{\text{Fourier}}(u, t) =$$

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{t_f}}u_0 + \sum_{k=1}^K [u_{2k}\frac{2}{\sqrt{t_f}}\cos(\omega_k t) + u_{2k-1}\frac{2}{\sqrt{t_f}}\sin(\omega_k t)]. \quad (20)$$

The frequencies $\omega_k = 2\pi k/t_f$, $k = 1, \dots, K$ have a maximum *cutoff* value at $2\pi K/t_f$, that must be chosen big enough to include the relevant natural frequencies of the spin qudit, but not so large that it cannot be handled experimentally. Some constraints have to be imposed on the allowed values for the parameters: the pulse amplitude must start and end at zero: $f(u, 0) = f(u, t_f) = 0$, which translates into $\sum_{k=1}^K u_{2k} = 0$. We have also imposed a zero value for the average amplitude, $\int_0^{t_f} dt f(u, t) = 0$, which translates into $u_0 = 0$. Finally, the generated magnetic field cannot have arbitrary amplitudes. One way to constrain it is to set a maximum value:

$$|\frac{2u_k}{\sqrt{t_f}}|b \leq b_{\text{max}}. \quad (21)$$

These constraints ensure that each frequency component does not surpass a given amplitude b_{\max} . It does not ensure, however, that the microwave field, composed of the sum of all components, surpasses that threshold. Depending on the experimental setup, however, it may happen that the field cannot surpass a given bound at any time. We have forced this constraint by also implementing an alternative parametrization consisting of a transformation of the Fourier series:

$$f(u, t) = \Phi(f_{\text{Fourier}}(u, t)), \quad (22)$$

where

$$\Phi(x) = b_{\max} \frac{x}{1 + |x|} \quad (23)$$

Of course, other similar transformation functions can be used, that ensure $|\Phi(x)| \leq b_{\max}$. Using a parametrization such as this, there is no need to impose a bound on the values of $|u_k|$.

We briefly summarize now the relevant equations for the simpler problem of point-to-point optimization. Some of the previous equations must then be replaced by other ones. In particular, the equation of motion to be controlled, instead of Eqs. (12) and (13), is Schrödinger's equation for a single state:

$$i \frac{\partial}{\partial t} |\psi(u; t)\rangle = f(u, t) \hat{V}(t) |\psi(u; t)\rangle, \quad (24)$$

$$|\psi(u; 0)\rangle = |\psi^0\rangle. \quad (25)$$

Often, the objective is the population of a target state $|\psi_{\text{target}}\rangle$, in which case the functional to be maximized is defined as:

$$F(\psi) = |\langle \psi | \psi_{\text{target}} \rangle|^2, \quad (26)$$

instead of the one given in Eq. (14). Therefore, the problem boils down to the maximization of: $G(u) = F(\psi(u, t_f))$. In this case, the gradient is given by:

$$\frac{\partial G}{\partial u_m}(u) = 2\text{Im} \int_0^{t_f} dt \frac{\partial f}{\partial u_m}(u; t) \langle \chi(u; t) | \hat{V}(t) | \psi(u; t) \rangle, \quad (27)$$

where the *costate* $|\chi(u; t)\rangle$ is now defined by:

$$i \frac{\partial}{\partial t} |\chi(u; t)\rangle = f(u, t) \hat{V}(t) |\chi(u; t)\rangle, \quad (28)$$

$$|\chi(u; t_f)\rangle = \langle \psi_{\text{target}} | \chi(u; t) \rangle |\psi_{\text{target}}\rangle. \quad (29)$$

In order to implement both the QOCT equations for the gate optimization and for the point-to-point transitions, we have used the qutip code as a base [60, 61]. We have, however, not employed the QOCT algorithms provided by this platform (at the time of writing of this article), but used the gradient, computed as in Eq. (17), to feed our own QOCT code [62], that then utilizes a general purpose function optimization algorithm: the Sequential Least-Squares Quadratic Programming (SLSQP) algorithm [63] as implemented in the NLOPT library [64].

III. RESULTS

A. The GdW₃₀ molecular spin qudit

In order to explore the potential of QOCT for the control of spin qudits, we have chosen a system, GdW₃₀ [27, 37], which is both well characterized and relatively simple. The molecular structure of this polyoxometalate cluster is shown in Fig. 1. It hosts a single Gd³⁺ ion and forms crystals with all molecules oriented in the same manner. In addition, magnetically diluted crystals can be grown by simply replacing Gd³⁺ with Y³⁺, which is chemically equivalent but diamagnetic. This allows enhancing spin coherence times up to 2 – 3 μs [37] while keeping the possibility of orienting the magnetic fields \vec{B} and \vec{b} along specific molecular axes. This molecule shows a hard magnetic axis along the main molecular axis z . Its static spin Hamiltonian can be well described by Eqs. (1), (2) and (3) with $S = 7/2$, $g = 2$, $D = 1281$ MHz and $E = 294$ MHz. The overall splitting of the $d = 8$ multiplet is smaller than 1 K, or 20.8 GHz, thus ensuring that adjacent level splittings lie within the reach of conventional EPR as well as of other microwave technologies. In all calculations discussed below, we have chosen the static magnetic field \vec{B} to point in the x direction (medium axis) and set $B = 0.15$ T. Under such conditions, the eigenstates of $\hat{H}_{\text{ZF}} + \hat{H}_{\text{Zeeman}}$ become close approximations to pure spin projections along \vec{B} . The time-dependent magnetic field \vec{b} is perpendicular, and points in the y direction (easy axis), thus inducing transitions between adjacent energy levels.

B. Transition implementation via monochromatic pulses

In this section, we discuss the manipulation of the GdW₃₀ spin using monochromatic pulses resonant with the set of allowed transitions mentioned above and shown in Fig. 1. As an illustration, we consider the application of π pulses linking every two of these states. Fig. 2 (top) displays the transformation infidelities (i.e. $1 - |\langle \psi(t_\pi^\lambda) | k \rangle|^2$) as a function of the time t_π^λ allocated to complete the operation, for the seven $|j\rangle \rightarrow |k = j + 1\rangle$ transitions. One can see that the error in the outcome state is reduced as $t_\pi^\lambda \rightarrow \infty$. In fact, from the logarithmic plot one may infer a quadratic behaviour:

$$1 - |\langle \psi(t_\pi^\lambda) | k \rangle|^2 = \mathcal{O}((1/t_\pi^\lambda)^2). \quad (30)$$

It becomes clear that, in order to ensure a given fidelity, a minimum time (or, equivalently, a maximum amplitude) is required.

FIG. 2. *Top*: Infidelities of the seven main resonant transitions in the GdW₃₀ molecule, as a function of the π -pulse time. *Bottom*: Infidelities of the seven main transitions in the GdW₃₀ molecule, as function of the total pulse time, for pulses obtained with optimal control. *Inset*: Time-dependent shape of the pulses used to generate two of those $|0\rangle \rightarrow |1\rangle$ transitions: one π -pulse (black), and one optimized pulse (red), corresponding to the thick black and red dots, respectively, on the blue lines.

C. Optimization of state-to-state transitions

In this and the following section, we apply the QOCT methods described in section II to quantum operations on GdW₃₀ having different targets. First, we optimize resonant transitions and sequences of these (in the next section we tackle the optimization of quantum gates). The goal here is to see how OCT permits to increase the fidelities shown in Fig. 2 (top), by allowing for the presence in the pulse of other frequencies, besides the resonant one. We have performed QOCT calculations [65] considering, for each transition, the same total propagation time used to create Fig. 2 (top). Each of these propagation times t_π^λ corresponds to a π -pulse amplitude λ [Eq. (9)], that we have used now to set a bound for the Fourier expansion coefficients in the OCT maximization: the temporal shape of the microwave field is given

FIG. 3. Infidelities for the $|0\rangle \rightarrow |7\rangle$ and $|0\rangle \rightarrow \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|0\rangle - i|7\rangle)$ transitions, as a function of operation time, for the pulses obtained as a sequence of monochromatic resonant pulses (π or $\pi/2$), and for the optimal pulses obtained with QOCT.

by Eq. (20), where $|\frac{2u_j}{\sqrt{t_\pi^\lambda}}| \leq \lambda$. We have therefore used for this first set of calculations the first parametrization described in Section II C, i.e. Eq. (20).

Having in mind the level splitting present in GdW₃₀ and typical experimental capabilities, we have set the frequency cutoff at 8 GHz (the maximum frequency allowed in the parameter search space). The resulting (in) fidelities are displayed in Fig. 2 (bottom). The shaped pulses permit to decrease those infidelities with respect to the simple π -pulse values, down to negligible values for all but the shortest total transition times (we have set a 10^{-7} threshold to stop the search algorithm, and hence the flat curves for the longer times). In Fig. 2 (inset), we also compare the shape of control pulses corresponding to a resonant transition (monochromatic π -pulse) and to the optimized one from states $|6\rangle$ to $|7\rangle$. These examples correspond to duration values marked by (respectively) black (top) and red dots (bottom). It is clear that the optimized pulse achieves a much better fidelity in a much shorter time.

Let us consider now the more general case of optimizing transitions between states, say $|n\rangle$ and $|m\rangle$, that are not directly coupled by the external field, i.e. $\langle n|S_y|m\rangle = 0$. A possible solution is to concatenate a series of π -pulses, between intermediate states. In fact, this is a criterion for universality: if any two states can be connected through others, the qudit can perform any unitary and, in this sense, can be regarded as a universal quantum processor. However, the time needed is proportional to the number of pulses, which in practice is a limitation. Thus, in this case, QOCT offers a clear advantage by replacing a single shaped pulse to achieve, and accelerate, a process that

would otherwise require a sequence of 7 monochromatic pulses.

In Fig. 3 we have tested this by comparing the infidelity in the transition $|0\rangle \rightarrow |7\rangle$, using a sequence of π -pulses between adjacent levels, $|k\rangle \rightarrow |k+1\rangle$, and using QOCT. The improvement is quite significant. In particular, we have run over a range of amplitudes λ , that determine the π -pulse length for each transition, $t_\pi^\lambda(k \rightarrow k+1)$. The full $|0\rangle \rightarrow |7\rangle$ process then requires $t_f = \sum_{k=0}^6 t_\pi^\lambda(k \rightarrow k+1)$. The plot displays the fidelity achieved with these pulse sequences. Then, for each of those times, we have performed QOCT calculations, once again setting a bound for the amplitudes of the individual Fourier terms equal to λ . The plot shows how, even at very short operation times, the fidelities achieved by the optimized pulses are almost equal to one. In terms of time scales, a 99 % fidelity can be achieved in less than 10 ns, thus much shorter than $T_2 \simeq 2 \mu\text{s}$, while reaching the same result with a sequence of monochromatic pulses would take more than 1 μs .

In Fig 3 we also show results of a similar calculation, but using the $|0\rangle \rightarrow \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|0\rangle - i|7\rangle)$ state as target, a superposition state that can be reached with a $\pi/2$ -pulse corresponding to the $|0\rangle \rightarrow |1\rangle$ transition, followed by the same previous sequence of π -pulses that raises the state through the next adjacent levels. The results are qualitatively similar to the ones obtained for the full $|0\rangle$ to $|7\rangle$ transition, thus showing that the speed enhancement achieved by the application of QOCT is not restricted to any particular class of transitions. This allows targeting the optimization of complex gates, which is discussed next.

We note that the pulses that have been optimized in this way to induce a given transition, would also affect other states. This is in contrast with monochromatic pulses, that only affect a given resonant transition. If one wishes to find an optimal, multi-frequency pulse that only affects one transition, leaving all other states invariant, one would have to use the control method for full evolution operator – as exemplified in the following section.

D. Quantum gate optimization

Finally, we proceed to our true objective: the search for non-trivial pulse shapes that realize quantum gates, with high fidelities, in short times. As target gates, we have chosen the family of Deutsch gates [66, 67]:

$$D(\theta) = \begin{bmatrix} I_6 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & i \cos(\theta) & \sin(\theta) \\ 0 & \sin(\theta) & i \cos(\theta) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (31)$$

where I_6 is the 6×6 identity matrix. Note that this family includes the Toffoli gate, for $\theta = \pi/2$. The reason for focusing on this set of gates is that it is universal: any circuit can be constructed by combination of these components.

FIG. 4. Optimal pulse in the time domain (top), and its power spectrum in the frequency domain (bottom) of the optimal pulse obtained for the $\theta = \pi/4$ Deutsch gate. The pulse parametrization used is the simple Fourier expansion given by Eq. (20).

These gates can be implemented with sequences of rotations induced with monochromatic pulses, but the necessary operation times may be inconveniently long. For example, following the procedure described in App. A, the Toffoli gate may be implemented through the following sequence:

$$D\left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right) = e^{i\frac{\pi}{8}} \hat{R}_Z^{(01)}\left(\frac{1}{4}\pi\right) \hat{R}_Z^{(12)}\left(\frac{1}{2}\pi\right) \hat{R}_Z^{(23)}\left(\frac{3}{4}\pi\right) \hat{R}_Z^{(34)}(\pi) \\ \hat{R}_Z^{(45)}\left(\frac{5}{4}\pi\right) \hat{R}_Z^{(56)}\left(\frac{3}{2}\pi\right) \hat{R}_Z^{(67)}\left(\frac{3}{4}\pi\right) \hat{R}_X^{(67)}(\pi) \quad (32)$$

The global $e^{i\frac{\pi}{8}}$ factor is physically irrelevant. As discussed above, the rotations around the Z axis cannot be directly implemented in the experimental setup that we are considering, but can be substituted by X and Y rotations with the well known composition $R_Z(\theta) = R_X(\pi/2)R_Y(\theta)R_X(-\pi/2)$. In this way, the final rotation tally is 22, which obviously translates into a very long operation time. In fact, if we set a minimum acceptable

FIG. 5. Optimal pulse in the time domain (top), and its power spectrum in the frequency domain (bottom), of the optimal pulse obtained for the Toffoli ($\theta = \pi/2$ Deutsch) gate. The pulse parametrization used is the one given by Eq. (22).

fidelity of 0.99 (using Eq. (14) as fidelity measure), the required time is more than $4 \mu\text{s}$, longer than the decoherence times of our experimental setup.

The use of multi-frequency pulses obtained with QOCT appears then as a possible way to speed up the operation and make it feasible in practice. We have searched for solution pulses using the two different parametrizations discussed in Section II C, which amounts to assuming the existence of different types of experimental constraints.

In a first example we have used the simple Fourier parametrization given in Eq. (20), in combination with the per-frequency amplitude constraint given in Eq. (21). This means that the optimizations are performed constraining the allowed parameter set, such that each sinusoidal (or cosinusoidal) term in the expansion (20) has a maximum amplitude. In the calculations shown here, we have set b_{max} to a relatively high value of 20 mT in order to make the operation, and therefore also the computational, times manageably short. However, we have performed simulations with lower thresholds, and

will discuss below the influence of b_{max} on t_f .

The total propagation time t_f for this first example was set to 20 times the maximum natural period of the field-free Hamiltonian, i.e. the period corresponding to the smallest transition frequency. For the choice of static magnetic field used here ($\vec{B} = 0.15T\vec{e}_x$), $t_f \sim 10$ ns. The optimization algorithm is an iterative process that we stop when the quality of the gate, measured as $F(\hat{U}(u; t_f)) = |\hat{U}(u, t_f) \cdot \hat{D}(\theta)|^2$, reaches a certain threshold, that for these calculations we have set to 0.99.

Figure 4 displays the results obtained for $\theta = \pi/4$ as an example (the results obtained for other angles are qualitatively similar). The top panel shows $f(u^{(0)}; t)$ in real time, whereas the bottom panels displays its power spectrum. Both plots demonstrate the complexity of the pulses, that do not have dominant frequencies.

The real-time evolution of the microwave field shows peaks of ≈ 30 mT. Even though one can ensure in the algorithm that each frequency component is below a fixed threshold, the real-time value is a sum of them all, and for this reason it may surpass that bound. The experimental setup, however, may be limited by the amplitude of the field in real time, and not in frequencies, and for this reason, we have also implemented the parametrization defined in Eq. (22), that we have used for our final sample calculation. In this case, the target was the Toffoli gate (the Deutsch gate with $\theta = \frac{\pi}{2}$), and we have enforced a b_{max} value of 3 mT. In this case, we required the operation time t_f to be longer, equal to 40 times the maximum natural period of the field-free Hamiltonian, or approximately 20 ns, in order to achieve the previously mentioned minimum fidelity of 0.99. The resulting optimal field, in both real time and in the frequency domain, is plotted in Fig. 5. It can be seen how the 3 mT amplitude bound is respected at all times.

In the previous examples, we have set a total operation time t_f and an amplitude bound b_{max} . These two magnitudes are of course related: if, for a given t_f , we set a too low amplitude bound, the quality of the gate (as measured by Eq. (14) will also be too low. In fact, if we fix a threshold for acceptable gate quality (say, 0.99), for each given propagation time there will be a minimum amplitude bound necessary for the QOCT algorithm to return a successful pulse. Even with optimal pulse shapes, we need a sufficiently high field amplitude in order to get a high quality gate. Whether this can be achieved depends on the given experimental setup chosen to implement the operations, and on its technical limitations.

We have therefore studied this issue by computing the minimum amplitude bound that can be used to constrain the QOCT calculation in order to get a given gate, as a function of operation time. The results are shown in Fig. 6. Those calculations were done with the first parametrization form, that forces the amplitude bound to each frequency component, but of course a similar plot could be obtained with the second one. This type of plot helps to ascertain whether or not the gate operations are experimentally feasible, as in practice there is a hardware

FIG. 6. Minimal bound on the amplitudes (y -axis) that allows to obtain a $\theta = \pi/2$ Deutsch gate for a given total operation time (x -axis).

bound on the field amplitudes that can be used. Given this limit, one may learn from the plot what operation times are feasible, even with shaped optimal pulses. Obviously, the lower the available amplitudes, the longer the operations times must be.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The previous results show that the use of complex pulses, engineered by optimal control techniques, provides a method for improving the speed of operations performed on spin qudits. The advantages are already noticeable for the realization of elementary transitions, when the application of monochromatic pulses is limited by the need of keeping the excitation amplitudes sufficiently low. Yet, they become even more important when dealing with more complex operations. Then, QOCT allows reaching any given fidelity of the outcome wave function with a single control pulse replacing the often long sequence of resonant pulses required by standard techniques. This possibility is especially relevant for algorithms that involve transitions between relatively disconnected states. For a necessarily limited coherence spin time, this difference can represent a big gain in the performance of such protocols.

The molecular qudit design and the way information is encoded on its spin states can be adapted to suit best the requirements of specific quantum protocols [18, 68], thus offering a vast choice of possible molecular platforms and implementations. Optimal control techniques described in this work are flexible enough to be made compatible with almost any of them. Although we have here considered a specific molecule for illustrative purposes, QOCT can deal with any spin model and with diverse control interactions (e.g. magnetic or electric field pulses). Therefore, it can be adapted to boost the implementation of diverse algorithms. We feel that it will be of special relevance to quantum error correction, because reaching a fidelity improvement with such protocols critically de-

pends on the ratio between the implementation time and T_2 . With an additional computational cost, one can even consider optimizing the control pulses to best compensate for the actual sources of decoherence in each molecule, mainly dephasing by nuclear spins located in the ligand shell surrounding the magnetic core.

The use of more sophisticated control pulses represents a challenge to experimental implementations. Most commercial EPR systems work with relatively narrow excitation bands and a reduced choice of pulse shapes. In recent years such systems have been complemented with waveguide generators able to arbitrarily design the excitation pulses [69–71]. In addition, some systems allow the use of relatively high microwave field amplitudes [72]. Still, these set-ups are limited to frequencies lying sufficiently close to the cavity resonance frequency. In order to expand the frequency window, one can resort to on-chip circuits, with the excitation being driven by an open transmission line. This scheme, illustrated by Fig. 1, has been applied to investigate coherent control of NV centers in diamond [73] and to perform broadband spectroscopy of GdW_{30} and other molecular spin qudits [22, 27]. It can also be used to read out the outcome, either by looking at the frequency dependent absorption, in a projective measurement, or by coupling it to a superconducting resonator that can perform nondemolition, dispersive measurements of the qudit states [74]. Some experimental systems combining superconducting resonators and broadband control lines have been recently reported [75]. The main limitation of these systems is that microwave field amplitudes higher than 1–3 mT are difficult to achieve, on account of the bounds to the microwave power input associated with the attenuation of the input lines, which increases with frequency, and with the critical current density in the case of superconducting circuits [76]. Another promising implementation is based on the combination of single-molecule electronics with gates or coils able to locally generate arbitrarily shaped electric or magnetic microwave pulses. Experiments performed on molecules trapped between point contacts or between a metal substrate and a STM tip have provided measurements of spin coherence in individual molecules [77] and achieved the realization of Grover’s search algorithm using three nuclear spin states in a Tb-based molecule [28]. One of the advantages of optimal control techniques is that they can easily incorporate bounds associated with experimental limitations, in either frequency or intensity of the time-dependent perturbation, thus they provide the optimal control adapted to each specific situation.

In summary, the application of quantum optimal control theory to operate the states of molecular spin qudits offers remarkable prospects to improve their performance, compensating for their not too long coherence times. Equipped with these techniques, many more molecular systems and applications can become feasible, thus contributing to an alternative and promising path towards large scale quantum computation and simulation.

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Appendix A: Generation of unitary operations

As it has been stated in Sec. IIB, one can decompose any unitary matrix $\hat{U} \in U(d)$ into a sequence of two-state rotations (such as the ones given by Eq. (6)), which can then be physically realized – albeit approximate – by monochromatic pulses. The technique behind this procedure is the QR decomposition algorithm with Givens rotations [57, 58]. A Givens rotation is defined as $\hat{G}^{(jk)} = \hat{g}^{(jk)} \oplus \hat{i}^{(j\bar{k})}$, with $\hat{g}^{(jk)}$ being a complex 2x2 unitary matrix. In our case,

$$\hat{g}^{(jk)} = \hat{R}_{\vec{n}}^{(jk)}(\theta) = \begin{bmatrix} c & s \\ -s^* & c \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{A1})$$

with $c = \cos(\theta/2)$, $s = -i \sin(\theta/2)e^{i\varphi}$ and $\varphi = \arg \mu_{jk} + \phi$. In the following, we will refer to the complete matrix $\hat{G}^{(jk)} = \hat{R}_{\vec{n}}^{(jk)}(\theta) \oplus \hat{i}^{(j\bar{k})}$ just as $\hat{R}_{\vec{n}}^{(jk)}(\theta)$ to lighten the notation.

The algorithm determines a sequence of Givens rotations that transforms the original unitary matrix into a diagonal matrix. Physically, each rotation operates on each pair of levels as the original unitary dictates. The final diagonal matrix that we get accounts for the relative phases that arise between levels during the process. These phases can then be corrected with a final sequence of diagonal rotations (\hat{R}_Z rotations).

Therefore, we apply a sequence of these rotations to the conjugate transpose of our problem matrix [78], \hat{U}^\dagger , and obtain a diagonal form, \hat{D} :

$$\hat{D} = \prod_l \hat{R}_{\vec{n}_l}^{(j_l k_l)}(\theta_l) \hat{U}^\dagger \quad (\text{A2})$$

Here, we take from each column c of \hat{U}^\dagger the elements $(\hat{U}^\dagger)_{j_l c_l}$ and $(\hat{U}^\dagger)_{k_l c_l}$ ($j_l < k_l$) and we use them to compute the rotation parameters as it is shown in Algorithm 1. This algorithm proceeds by making zeros in the left-bottom corner of the matrix, until we end with the diagonal matrix \hat{D} . These rotations must obey the selection

rules of our molecule. Usually, these rules follow a ladder-type coupling (connecting levels j and $j+1$), that is why the algorithm takes that form for computing θ_l and \vec{n}_l .

The resulting diagonal matrix \hat{D} can then be decomposed as a product of diagonal rotations:

$$\hat{D}^\dagger = \prod_m \hat{R}_Z^{(j_m k_m)}(\beta_m) \quad (\text{A3})$$

This decomposition will consist of, at most, $d-1$ rotations corresponding to $d-1$ relative phases, β_m , as well as an extra global phase, β , which is physically irrelevant. If \hat{R}_Z is not implementable in our experimental setup, we can generate it through three X and Y rotations, as mentioned in Sec. IIB.

At the end, the unitary decomposition reads:

$$\hat{U} = e^{i\beta} \prod_m \hat{R}_Z^{(j_m k_m)}(\beta_m) \prod_l \hat{R}_{\vec{n}_l}^{(j_l k_l)}(\theta_l) \quad (\text{A4})$$

The procedure just explained is illustrated schematically as follows, which is the algorithm used to derive Eq. (32) in the main text.

Algorithm 1 Unitary decomposition, adapted from Refs. [11, 57, 58].

- 1: $\hat{V} \leftarrow \hat{U}^\dagger$
 - 2: **for** $j = d, c = 0, j > c, c < d-1$ **do**
 - 3: $(r, c, s) \leftarrow (\sqrt{|U_{jc}|^2 + |U_{j-1c}|^2}, U_{j-1c}/r, -U_{jc}/r)$
 - 4: $(\theta, \varphi) \leftarrow (2 \arctan(|s/c|), \pi/2 + \arg[s] - \arg[c])$
 - 5: Store these parameters (θ, φ)
 - 6: $\hat{V} \leftarrow \hat{R}_{\vec{n}}^{(j-1, j)}(\theta) \hat{V}$
 - 7: **end for**
 - 8: $\hat{V} \leftarrow \arg[\text{diag}(\hat{V})]$
 - 9: Solve

$$\begin{bmatrix} -1/2 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 1 \\ 1/2 & -1/2 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1/2 & -1/2 & \dots & 0 & 1 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & -1/2 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 1/2 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \beta_1 \\ \beta_2 \\ \beta_3 \\ \vdots \\ \beta_{d-1} \\ \beta \end{bmatrix} = \hat{V}$$
 - 10: Store these phases β_i
-

Several comments are relevant. First, the number of rotations required depends on the dimension, d , and the structure of the unitary itself, \hat{U} , and on the connectivity between levels. Second, the decomposition is not unique. There may be alternative algorithms leading to different sequences. In fact, even the same algorithm may lead to a different rotation sequence, because some of the steps are very sensitive to the numerical precision of the calculations.

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